

Decomposition of Ce(IV) Chloride Complex: Kinetic Study in Perchloric Acid Medium

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The red-coloured complex formed by the interaction of ceric perchlorate and HCl in a high concentration of HCl is unstable and decomposes gradually. The kinetics of the decomposition obeys first order law. The activation energy and the entropy of activation are found to be 6.3 kcal./mole and -38 (E.U.) respectively.

It is well known that Ce(IV) forms complexes with some inorganic anions like perchlorate, sulphate, nitrate, and chloride and the oxidation potential of Ce(IV) depends on the acidity and particularly on the kinds of anion present. In a previous communication¹ the present authors have studied the kinetics of the decomposition of the chloro complex of Ce(IV) in sulphuric acid medium and found the decomposition reaction to be a first order one. In the present communication the authors have studied the kinetics of the decomposition of the chloro complex formed by the interaction of ceric perchlorate in HClO₄ and HCl, when the concentration of HCl is high.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials employed were of the highest purity available. Hydrochloric acid used was of 'AnalaR variety. Ceric perchlorate was prepared by electrolytic oxidation of cerous perchlorate, as suggested by Smith². Ceric ammonium nitrate (AnalaR) was employed as the starting material. Nitrates were eliminated during the process. The salt was heated with HClO₄ and H₂O, to reduce it to the trivalent state. Then it was taken to fumes of HClO₄ and was finally converted into ceric perchlorate by electrolytic oxidation. The solution was stored in a refrigerator until required for use when it was diluted to the desired concentration. It was then standardised against sodium oxalate.

The decomposition of the complex was followed in a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter, using green filters¹.

Measurement of Optical Density.—The optical density of the complex at zero time cannot be measured accurately as it decomposes gradually as soon as it is formed. In practice, in all experiments 2 ml of ceric perchlorate solution was mixed with an equal volume of HCl of desired concentration in colorimetric test tubes and the changes in optical density were followed with time.

Order of Reaction.—The order of the decomposition reaction of the complex was determined at three HCl concentrations, viz., 6*N*, 5*N*, and 4*N*. The concentrations of ceric perchlorate used was exactly $M/20$. The change in optical density was followed in the colorimeter with time (Table II). The plot of $\log \{(O.D.)_t - (O.D.)_0\}$ against time, where $(O.D.)_t$ and $(O.D.)_0$ are optical densities at any time t and that of the doubly diluted ceric perchlorate solution respectively, yields a straight line. This indicates that the reaction

1. This Journal, 1963, 40, 217.

2. Smith and Duke, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 15, 120; 1955, 27, 1144.

is first order with respect to coloured complex. From the slopes of the linear plots the velocity constants were calculated (vide any individual curve of Fig. 1).

Time (sec.).

FIG. 1.

Curves 1—4 represent $M/10 - \text{Co}^{++}$ in equal volume each of

- (1) Water + 6N.HCl
- (2) $F/2 \text{HClO}_4$ + ..
- (3) $F \text{HClO}_4$ + ..
- (4) $2F \text{HClO}_4$ + ..

Time (min.).

FIG. 2

Curves 1—3 represent respectively $M/10 - \text{Co}^{++}$ with 12N.HCl (1:1) at

- (1) 20°.
- (2) 25°.
- (3) 32°.

Effect of HClO_4 .—The decomposition of the complex was retarded by HClO_4 . Here in all the cases, concentrations of Co^{++} and HCl were kept fixed. The acidity was varied by addition of HClO_4 . $\log K$ against $\log [\text{H}^+]$ in HClO_4 plot was found to yield a straight line and the product $K [\text{H}^+]$ provided a fairly constant value. These are evident from Fig. 3 and column 6 of Table I respectively.

Log $[\text{H}^+]$ →
FIG. 3 $1/T \times 10^{-4}$ →
FIG. 4

Effect of Temperature.—The velocity constants were calculated at three different temperatures, viz., 32°, 25°, and 20° (Fig. 2). All these experiments were performed at identical H^+ ion concentration and $\log K$ was then plotted against $1/T$ (Fig. 4). The apparent activation energy was calculated to be 6.3 kcal./mole from the linear plot. Using this value of the activation energy, the average entropy of activation is found to be -38 (E.U.).

TABLE I

Ceric perchlorate= $M/20$. HCl= $6N$. Temp.= 32° .

No.	[H ⁺].	Log [H ⁺].	K (sec ⁻¹).	Log K .	$\bar{K}[\text{H}^+] \times 10^2$.
1	1.312	0.1179	0.04376	$\bar{2}.6411$	5.741
2	1.784	0.2340	0.03680	$\bar{2}.5664$	6.722
3	2.180	0.3385	0.02764	$\bar{2}.4415$	6.025
4	2.939	0.4682	0.02149	$\bar{2}.3323$	6.301

TABLE II

Temp.= 20° . (O.D.)₀=0.13. Ce perchlorate= $M/20$.

HCl = $6N$.		HCl = $5N$.		HCl = $4N$.	
Time.	O.D.	Time.	O.D.	Time.	O.D.
30 sec.	1.24	30 sec.	1.20	30 sec.	0.88
60	0.68	40	0.81	48	0.67
90	0.36	60	0.58	60	0.44
120	0.26	78	0.42	78	0.32
150	0.21	90	0.34	90	0.27
180	0.19	106	0.24	106	0.22
210	0.16	120	0.19	120	0.18
240	0.15	150	0.16	136	0.16

DISCUSSION

The overall reaction between Ce(rv) and HCl consists of the following three stages:

1. Interaction of Cl⁻ ion with Ce⁴⁺ to form a complex compound.
2. Decomposition of the complex compound.
3. Reduction of ceric to cerus by HCl.

The kinetics of the second step, i.e., the decomposition of the complex, has been studied. The optical density was followed with time and change in the optical density, i.e., $\{(O.D.)_t - (O.D.)_0\}$ was worked out in the following way.

The ceric perchlorate solution shows a definite amount of absorption. When mixed with an equal volume of HCl (conc.), a deep red solution is formed which disappears soon; the original colour of the solution is restored which again in course of time vanishes due to formation of cerous salt. Since the increase in optical density from the initial value, i.e., half diluted ceric perchlorate solution, is due to the formation of the complex only, the concentration of the complex at any instant is simply the difference between the optical density of red-coloured complex (O.D.)_t and the optical density of the half-diluted ceric perchlorate solution (O.D.)₀. Therefore the disappearance of the red-coloured complex and its concentration are characterised by the value of $\log(\text{complex}) \propto \log \{(O.D.)_t - (O.D.)_0\}$.

Unlike in sulphuric acid medium, the chloro complex in perchloric acid medium decomposes with a much faster speed because of the fact that Ce (rv) ion associates with sulphate ion to form successively^{3,4} Ce (SO₄)²⁺, Ce(SO₄)₂, and Ce (SO₄)₃⁻.

3. Hardwick and Robertson, *Canad. J. Res.*, 1951, 518, 828.

4. Moore and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 187.

In concentrated ceric sulphate solution, practically all the cerium will be present as $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3^{2-}$ and will form a strong complex. On the other hand, perchlorate ion is a least complex-forming anion. Hence ceric sulphate will react more slowly with HCl than ceric perchlorate and subsequently the complex, which is formed by the interaction of ceric perchlorate and HCl (conc.), will decompose with a much faster speed.

In an earlier communication¹ it has been shown that the activation energy in the case of sulphuric acid medium is approximately 19 kcal./mole. But here in perchloric acid medium, the energy is 6.3 kcal./mole. This is in accordance with the explanation given above.

It is evident from Table II that with decreasing HCl concentration, the optical density for a constant $\text{Ce}(\text{IV})$ concentration always diminishes. From a plot of $\log \{(O.D.)_t - (O.D.)_0\}$ against time (not shown here), it is noticed that the slopes of the straight lines are almost constant. This infers that though the reaction rate at a constant temperature is independent of the acid concentration, the amount of complex formation is greater with the addition of higher concentrations of HCl.

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